

SUCCESS STORIES

Adoption of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits Recommended Technologies by Farmers

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Application of Stage Based Nutrition Increases Yield and Profit in Banana and Sapota

Being perennial in nature, fruit crop growers of banana and sapota apply fertilizers only in two splits during monsoon. However, it is advised to apply the fertilizers in three or four split doses by the ICAR-AICRP Centre at Fruit Research Station, Gandevi, Navsari, Gujarat based on the experiments conducted by it. This advice was well taken by the two young farmers, Shri. Milan Naik, a banana growing farmer and Shri. Bhargav Wadnerkar, a sapota growing farmer in Gandevi.

The young banana farmer, Shri. Milan Naik previously applied fertilizers (NPK) after 3rd, 4th and 5th months of planting and was getting average fruit bunch weight as 28-30 kg/plant. Now after consulting with ICAR-AICRP (Fruits), Gandevi Centre, he applies 80% N and K₂O fertilizer in four split 3rd, 5th, 7th and 9th months after planting in different ratios of recommended technology (80% of the recommended dose of nitrogen and potash, *i.e.* 240 g N and 160 g K₂O /plant, out of which first installment, 96 g N and 40 g K₂O at 3rd

Milan K Naik

month during vegetative stage, second installment 72 g N and 56 g K₂O at the 5th month during flower bud initiation stage, third installment 72 g N and 40 g K₂O at 7th month during flowering stage and fourth installment 0 g N and 24 g K₂O at 9th month during bunch development. And FYM 10 kg/plant and total dose of P₂O₅ @ 90g/plant at the time of planting. With the adoption of this production technology and use of bio-fertilizers under the guidance of the center in 2016, the farmer now gets about average fruit bunch weight of 32-35 kg/plant from 2016 onwards with additional monetary returns of about rupees 12,000 per hectare (with the increase in yield and reduction in cost of fertilizer inputs).

In South Gujarat conditions, round the year sapota has overlapping flowering and fruiting. Shri. Bhargav Wadnerkar a hard working young farmer from Gandevi, Navsari in Gujarat grows Kalipatti variety of Sapota in 30 years old 3 ha orchard under spacing of 10 x 10 m. Like any other sapota growers in his district, he was applying fertilizers only twice in limited quantity in the form of NPK during June – October and was getting fruit yield (150-

Bhargav S Wadnerkar

170 kg/tree). When he visited Fruit Research Station, Gandevi, Navsari in 2013, he learnt about the benefit of stage based application of fertilizers as per need. He was advised to apply 100% recommended dose of fertilizers in ring method @ 1000-500-500g NPK/tree/year to adult trees in three splits, *i.e.* 250-500-125g NPK/tree in June, 500-00-250g NPK/tree in August and 250-00-125g NPK/tree in October. Also, it was suggested to

him to apply FYM @ 100 kg/ha during the month of June. With this small intervention, he now gets about 180-200 kg/tree fruit yield yearly since 2015 with additional income of rupees 20,000-30,000 per hectare when compared to the old practice of two splits. This technology of three split dose practice which is working very well in his sapota field had encouraged other six sapota growers in the district to adopt it. The technology adopters says that their regular visits to the ICAR-AICRP (Fruits) centre at Gandevi during the Krishi Mahosav programme and other programmes, and also being in regular communication with the scientists for guidance, suggestions and information about new packages of practices helped them to grow fruit crops profitably.

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Bhargav S Wadnerkar, Khakhwada, Gandevi, Navsari, Gujarat. Mobile: 9638464242

With inputs from Dr. A. N. Patel, Dr. K. D. Bisane, Mr. B. M. Naik and Mr. A. R. Patel, Fruit Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Gandevi, Navsari 396360, Gujarat.

Neem oil based botanical insecticides manages sapota bud borer profitably

Bud borer of sapota causes considerable damage and reduces profitability. However, the sapota growers in the Navsari district avoid spraying of any pesticides in sapota due to cost constraints. Therefore, an alternative bio-pesticide, neem oil based botanical insecticide Nimbecidine is recommended. This organic pesticide suppress pest infestation as it acts as antifeedant, repellent and ovi-position deterrent.

Two progressive farmers, Shri. Mukeshchandra Desai and his brother Shri. Rohitbhai Desai were growing sapota in their 30 years old orchard which is very well known for its good quality fruits. However, in 2008 their Kalipatti variety orchard of 10 x 10 m spaced was infested with bud borers and yield was drastically reduced. They were thinking of organic pest control measures. In 2010, when they visited ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, Gandevi centre to know about organic

Mukeshchandra Ramanlal Desai and Rohitbhai R. Desai

chemicals for controlling the bud borers. The entomologist at the centre had advised to use botanical pesticides and recommended spraying of Nimbecidine @ 0.3 % after 2nd fortnight in the month of March which is the phase of new flowering flush in sapota orchards. They were advised to apply the botanical formulation 3-4 times at 20 days interval with the addition of detergent powder as a sticker to get better results. With the adoption of this recommended pest management technology. They could find that there is no difference in fruit yield during the first 2 years when compared with the orchards in which chemicals were sprayed. However after 3 years of continuous spraying of botanical products, they found that there was increase in the yield due to pest control and were getting higher price of fruits in wholesale market because of its good quality. In their orchards, with the use of botanical products, there were no pest problems due to increased number of natural enemies like spiders, mantises, etc. These two farmers now are getting additional income of rupees 8,000-10,000 per hectare with the adoption of this new practice over old practice and also influenced their relatives to use botanical products for their sapota orchards.

Farmers's contact details:

Shri. Mukeshchandra Ramanlal and Shri Rohitbhai R. Desai, Hond Post, Chikhali Taluk, Navsari, Gujarat. Mob.: 9825106062

With inputs from Dr. A. N. Patel, Dr. K. D. Bisane, Mr. B. M. Naik and Mr. A. R. Patel. Fruit Research Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Gandevi, Navsari 396360, Gujarat.

PAU Fruit Fly Traps: A Success Story of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits

The ICAR-AICRP on Fruits demonstrated the usefulness of a cost effective para pheromone fruit fly trap technology developed by one of its centres, Punjab Agricultural University (PAU) for the control of fruit fly damage in different fruit crops. Fruit flies are the major pests of several fruit and vegetable crops throughout the tropical and subtropical world amounting to an estimate loss of Rs. 6000 crores annually in India alone.

In Punjab, *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) and *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) are very important pests of fruit crops viz. citrus spp., guava, peach, pear, ber, plum, mango, loquat, sapota, fig, jamun, wild fig, phalsa, papaya, grapes, ripe bananas, pomegranate and litchi fruits causing damage to a

Cost effective eco-friendly trap for management of fruit flies in fruit crops

Rate: Rs. 100/trap

16 traps/acre

TIME OF FIXING TRAPS IN ORCHARDS*

Peach	1 st week of May
Pear	1 st week of June
Guava	1 st week of July
Kinnow	2 nd week of August

**Dates may be adjusted according to coming break stage of fruit*

Contact:
 Dr. Sandeep Singh, Assistant Entomologist,
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 0161-2401960 Ext. 303 (Fruit Science)
 E-mail: sandeep_pau.1974@pau.edu Booking can be done on phone or e-mail

P.A.U. FRUIT FLY TRAP
ਪੀ ਏ ਯੂ . ਫਰੂਟ ਫਲਾਈ ਟਰੈਪ

• ਫਲਾਂ ਦੀ ਮੁੱਖੀ ਦੀ ਵਾਹਾਵਾਹ-ਮੁੱਖੀ
 ਕਿਸਾਨਾਂ ਲਈ ਭਾਰੀ ਖਿਚ ਲਾਭਦੇ ਲਈ ਟਰੈਪ
 • 16 ਟਰੈਪ ਪ੍ਰਤੀ ਏਕੜ
 • ਮੁੱਲ: 100 ਰੁਪਏ ਪ੍ਰਤੀ ਟਰੈਪ

*** ਟਰੈਪਾਂ ਨੂੰ ਬਾਗਾਂ ਵਿੱਚ ਲਗਾਓ ਦਾ ਸਮੇਂ**

ਪੀਚ	ਮਈ ਦੇ ਪਹਿਲੇ ਹਫ਼ਤੇ
ਪੀਰ	ਜੂਨ ਦੇ ਪਹਿਲੇ ਹਫ਼ਤੇ
ਗੁਆਵਾ	ਜੁਲਾਈ ਦੇ ਪਹਿਲੇ ਹਫ਼ਤੇ
ਕਿਨੋਵ	ਅਗਸਤ ਦੇ ਦੂਜੇ ਹਫ਼ਤੇ

**ਟਰੈਪਾਂ ਨੂੰ ਫਲ ਦੇ ਚੱਲ ਰਹੇ ਹੋਣ ਦੇ ਮੁਤਾਬਕ ਫਲ ਲਗਾਓ*

ਮੁੱਖ ਮੁੱਲ: ਡਾ. ਸਾਂਦੀਪ ਸਿੰਘ, ਮੁੱਖ ਮੁੱਲ
 ਵਿਭਾਗ, ਫਲ ਵਿਗਿਆਨ ਵਿਭਾਗ,
 ਪੰਜਾਬ ਖੇਤੀਬਾੜੀ ਯੂਨੀਵਰਸਿਟੀ, ਲੁਧਿਆਣਾ (ਪੰਜਾਬ)
 ਮ. ਗੁਰਪ੍ਰਤਾਪ ਸਿੰਘ ਮੋਬਾਇਲ: 98888-86072
 88723-99221 ਫੋਨ 0161-2401960
 Ext. 303 (ਫਲ ਵਿਗਿਆਨ ਵਿਭਾਗ)
 ਈਮੇਲ: sandeep_pau.1974@pau.edu ਆਰਡਰ ਕਰ ਸਕਦੇ ਹੋ।

greater extent causing up to 100 per cent crop loss. It was observed that these fruit flies cause damage of 70-80 per cent in Kinnow mandarin, up to 100 per cent in rainy season guava, 30 per cent in mango, 70-80 per cent in peach, 80 per cent in soft pear, 50-60 per cent in hard pear and 30-40 per cent in plum. Besides the direct damage to fruits, fruit flies also cause great economic losses due to quarantine restrictions because of the infestation. Many a times, mere presence of the flies in a country could also restrict the free trade and export of fresh horticultural produce to large lucrative markets.

It was reported that due to EU ban on mangoes import from India in the year 2014 due to fruit flies, the Indian traders incurred an estimate loss of more than Rs. 100 crores. To control the fruit flies damage, farmers has to incur huge expenditure and the application of insecticides disrupts the ecosystem and causes numerous hazards, which in the present scenario warrants the need for an integrated approach for fruit fly management. Among the various alternate strategies available for the management of fruit flies, the use of methyl eugenol traps stands as the most outstanding alternative. This technique has been successfully used for the eradication and control of several *Bactrocera* sp. in several parts of the world. In this direction, the Scientists from PAU have developed a fruit fly trap, under ICAR-AICRP on Fruits from 2005 to 2013 and used for eco-friendly management of fruit flies on Kinnow Mandarin in Punjab. Research Evaluation Committee of the PAU, Ludhiana had approved the recommendation for fruit growers of Punjab in December 2013 on Kinnow, guava, pear and peach @ 16 traps per acre. In December 2015, PAU has recommended traps for management of fruit flies in mango and plum also. The PAU started selling "PAU Fruit Fly Trap" from April 2014 onwards to the fruit growers of Punjab @ Rs. 100 per trap. And till date, 15781 traps worth Rs. 15.8 lakhs had been supplied to fruit growers, covering an area of 986 acres.

With inputs from Dr. Sandeep Singh, Assistant Entomologist, Department of Fruit Science, PAU, Ludhiana

Nutrient Management in Banana Helps Assam Farmer Profitably

The Jorhat centre of the ICAR-AICRP on Fruits guided a young marginal farmers who has 2 bigha¹ (~670 Sq. Mt.) under banana cultivation with local variety during 2014-15. During an interaction with the young farmer, it was learnt that he haphazardly using fertilizers for his banana plantation and did not follow any proper nutrient management schedules. The scientists of the Jorhat Centre intervened and guided him on the scientific method of banana cultivation with special reference to 'nutrient management'. And the result is, at the end of the cropping season, the farmer earned a good profit (cost benefit ratio of new practice was 1:2.55 when compared to old practice which was 1: 1.35) during 2016-17.

The young farmer, Sri Ajit Bora belongs to Charingia village of Kathalguri. He is a marginal farmer and has 15 bigha (~5000 Sq. Mt.) of cultivated land out of which he grows banana in 2 bigha and rest is with paddy and vegetables. Apart from this, he has a small tea garden. This farmer was given proper guidance by the ICAR-AICRP on Fruits Jorhat Centre on production technology of banana by making frequent visits to his field and also over phone. This support had built confidence in him and he got encouraged to know more about the knowhow of scientific cultivation of banana, particularly on use of judicious nutrients was spread by him to other farmers from nearby villages and they now collect suckers from his farm with an aim to replicate the technology.

Ajit Bora

Farmer's Contact Details:

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With inputs from Dr. Kartik Baruah & Dr. Debanand Das, ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, Jorhat Centre, Assam.

¹ Bigha is a traditional unit of land in some parts of South Asia

Manjeri Nendran as an alternative to Nedunedran Banana

Facing with problems in cultivating Nedunendran a clone of Nendran with respect to the pests and diseases especially *Eumusae* leaf spot, Sri. C.M. Joy, a banana farmer from a middle class family in Thrissur contacted the scientists of Kannara centre of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits to find out more effective management practices for pests and diseases. At the centre, the scientists had recommended cultivation of Manjeri Nendran in 2015. He was supplied with the tissue culture planting materials of the variety for Field Level Demonstration. This variety was evaluated at the centre along with other nine Nendran clones and found having distinguishingly superior characters over most prevailing variety 'Nendran' in Kerala like hands per bunch and fingers per bunch were more resulting in higher yield. He also reported lesser incidence of *Eumusae* leaf spot in Manjeri Nendran.

C.M. Joy

The farmer got convinced with the superior performance of Manjeri Nendran from his one acre of demo field. He got 32 % additional yield for Manjeri Nendran compared to Nedunendran in 2016. The net benefit was Rs. 8.96 lakhs/ha (2.72 B:C ratio) with the Manjeri Nendran when compared to the old practice (Nedunendran) which was having a net benefit of Rs. 5.46 lakhs/ha (2.06 B:C ratio). Additional income v/s old practice – RS. 3.5 lakhs / ha The farmer was very much impressed with the performance of Manjeri Nendran in comparison with Nedunendran and is now cultivating it on a large scale and is also supplying planting materials to local progressive farmers as well. Now the area under Manjeri Nendran is about 100 acres in the Malappuram and Thrissur districts of Kerala. With the supply of quality planting material and with scientific advice on the cultivation practices for the variety at all phonological stages.

Farmers' contact details:

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With inputs from Dr. Rema Menon, Horticulturist (Retd.), AICRP (Fruits), Kannara, KAU.

Hasta bahar management in acid lime yields four folds profit in Vidarbha region

The management technology for regulation of flowering in acid lime (hasta bahar management) recommended suitable for this region based on the results of ICAR-AICRP on Fruits at Akola, was popularized by the KVK Akola through 13 field level demonstrations (FLD) in Patur area of Vivara village in the Akola district during year 2014-15. In the FLD more than 100 acid lime growers of Akola district who are growing in more than 2500 ha were involved.

One of the FLDs of a technology which involves spraying the acid lime trees with GA 50 ppm in the month of June and then subjecting the trees for water stress for 45 days (1st Sept. to 15 Oct.) and spraying with Cycocel 2000 ppm during the stress period (September) and application of nutrition had helped a farmer to get a net profit of four lakhs per hectare in 2016 from his 4.5 ha orchard. In this technology, half dose of required nitrogen, full dose of phosphorus and potassium only is applied at the time of release of stress and remaining half dose of nitrogen one month. Though the cost of production had increased with the adoption of this technology to the tune of Rs. 1 lakh/ha, it had yielded Rs. 4 lakh/ha making the benefit cost ratio of 5. This summer cropping technology of acid lime gained popularity among the farmers due to the instant results and many fold gain in profit. As of now, about 30% of farmers are following this technology as it is very simple to adopt and there is a great demand for summer (march-may) acid lime fruits.

Vinod Shirsagar

The economics of adopted technology is as follows:

Particulars	Old practice	New technology
Summer cropping yield (qt /ha)	75.00	187.50
Return Rs/ha	2.00	5.00
Cost of production (Rs /ha)	0.75	1.00
Net Profit (Rs Lakhs/ha)	1.25	4.00
Benefit/Cost ratio	2.66	5.00

Farmers' contact details: Vinod Shirsagar. Akola. Mobile: 09970357456

With inputs from Dr. Gajanan Tupkari, Dr.Dinesh H.Paithankar, Dr.Prakash Nagre, KVK Akola; Mr. Vinod Shirsagar & Mr. Devidas Dhotre (farmers)

Adoption of GAP on tissue culture banana cv. Grand Naine yields profitable income to Kalavalapalli farmer

Sri. M. Murali Krishhna a progressive banana farmer from Kalavalapalli village who adopts scientific technologies in farming has a cropping system with banana, coconut, cocoa, pineapple, oil palm, guava etc. During 2008-09, he learnt about new technologies through the demonstrations of the Horticultural Research Station (HRS), Kovvur about the package of practices on fertilizer application, drip irrigation, micronutrient sprays especially sulphate of potash, pest and disease management, bunch sleeving, etc. developed by scientists

Murali Krishhna

of HRS, Kovvur. This farmers adopted the new practices and is gaining good profits from the banana cultivation since 2011-12 from his 10 acres of area. He acquired knowledge on importance of organic cultivation practices, biological control agents, awareness on environmental pollution and its hazards. He was supported by the HRS, Kovvur in terms of supply of tissue culture plants, continuous guidance on timely technological interventions (especially spraying of sulphate of potash and bunch sleeving) supervision by scientists at the time of implementation. The farmer with the adoption of technology, spraying of sulphate of potash and bunch sleeving, from the Plant crop, he had gained income of Rs. 48,000/- in addition to the existing old practice income Rs. 96,675/- (Benefit cost ratio: 1.19) and from the first ratoon, income of Rs. 1,05,000/- in addition to Rs. 2,35,795/- from old practice (Benefit cost ratio: 3.12). This technology of spraying sulphate of potash and bunch sleeving is being adopted by 25-30% of banana farmers in Andhra Pradesh and also by the farmers of adjoining districts of Orissa, Telangana and Chhattisgarh.

Farmer's contact details:

Sri. M. Murali Krishhna, Kalavalapalli - 534301, West Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh.
Ph. No: +919440583725

With inputs from Dr. B.V.K. Bhagavan, Principal Scientist (Hort.) & Head, Dr. J. Krishna Prasadji Senior Scientist (Plant Pathology), Horticultural Research Station, Kovvur.

Additional Income with Mango Hybrid Amrapali and Banana BCB-3

In the year 2007, two medium poor farmers from Nadia, West Bengal, Sri Ranjit Debnath and Sri Sujit Debnath learnt about the mango hybrid, Amrapali during the scientists-farmers interaction at the ICAR-AICRP on Fruits, BCKV Centre at Gayeshpur Farm. In their 0.7 ha land, they had planted the hybrid and from 2011, they could get 30% additional income due to its regular bearing and more yields due to high density planting. The farmers were in regular contact with the AICRP scientists and got the encouragement for starting nursery of the hybrid which added to the additional income. Seeing the benefit and income, the farmers from the adjoining districts of the centre started adopting the hybrid.

Ranjit Debnath and Sujit Debnath

A farmer Sri Biswanath Ray, who cultivates banana plantation in the North 24 Parganas visited the institutional farm demonstration of Banana variety BCB-3 at the Mondouri Banana Research Station in 2008, he got impressed and expressed his desire to cultivate the variety BCB-3 in his 0.5 ha land. The scientists of the centre had provided all the necessary information and support with respect to the planting method of the improved variety, improved production and protection technology. With the support, intervention and encouragement of the centre's scientists he now sells excess suckers to the nearby farmers. With the new improved variety and supply of the suckers, he is now earning 25% additional income. Along with him now, there are five more farmers in the nearby areas started cultivating the variety, BCB-3 and is popular in Nadia and Hooghly, North 24 Parganas.

Biswanath Ray

Farmer's contact details:

Sri Ranjit Debnath and Sri Sujit Debnath, Golbazar, Gayeshpur, Nadia. Mobile No. 8017017872

Sri Biswanath Ray, Bhaluka, North 24 Parganas, Mobile No. 07890333306

With inputs from Dr. Kalyan Chakraborti and Dr. Pallab Datta; Dr. F.K. Bauri and Dr. D.K. Misra, BCKV, Mohanpur.

Rejuvenation of Old and Senile Mango Orchard Brings Cheers to Valsad Farmer

A progressive farmer, Mr. Rajesh Shah was worried due to continuous decrease in the yield and increased cost of cultivation from his 80 year old mango orchard having about 900 mango trees. In 2005, he even thought of selling it out and start establish a new orchard purchase on a new land.

During that time, he learnt about rejuvenation technique of old and senile mango orchard perfected by the scientists of ICAR-AICRP Centre at Agricultural Experimental Station, (AES), Paria. He had visited the centre and upon got convinced

about the technique, decided to rejuvenate his old and senile mango orchard. In the first instance, he pruned 50 trees and later extended to whole orchard with the help of continued support from the scientific team of AES centre. Now he is most happy and is doing his mango business with complete satisfaction since 2009 (with benefit cost ratio 1:3.33). He had mastered the technique with the support of the ICAR-AICRP team, AES, NAU, Paria to make the unproductive and became very popular among the mango farmers in his district and adjoining areas. First, he assigns numbers to each tree and then he identifies the branches to be removed based on observations like old branches, attacked by the pest/disease, bent from the trunk towards ground, and covered with the shadow of the adjacent trees. He keeps the branches for future canopy development at approx. 5.5 to 6.0 m distances above ground and then heads back the trees in July-August from underside with slant cut by using a sharp cutter for further growth. He advices the farmers to remove all the pruned wood from the orchard to avoid risk of pest infection from the garbage and to follow the instructions of scientists of ICAR-AICRP centre, Paria regarding fertilizer application, irrigation and other plant protection measures. Under his guidance and with the support of scientist at AES about 178 mango farmers have started canopy management of their old and senile orchards.

Rajeshbhai Ratanchand Shah

Farmers Contact Details:

Shri Rajeshbhai Ratanchand Shah, Kanadu Village, Umargam Taluk, Valsad 396140, Gujarat. Mobile: +91 98252 51012

With inputs from Dr. Hemant Sharma, Dr. J. K. Bana and Dr. P. D. Solanki, Agriculture Experimental Station, Navsari Agricultural University, Paria- 396145, Gujarat

Pruning Technology for High Density Planting In Mango

Periyakulam centre of the ICAR-AICRP had perfected pruning technology (2007 to 2012) for Alphonso mango under high density planting (HDP) of 5 x 5 m in which annual pruning of trees is headed back of 20 cm of terminal growth during the rest period immediately after harvest in June - July months before the emergence of new growth (floral or vegetative). This pruning technology was found to be more productive with the highest yield of 67.38 kg/tree and cost benefit ratio of 4.2:1. This production technology has been disseminated to the progressive mango growers by the scientists of Periyakulam centre.

Alphonso under HDP

In Sothuparai belt of Periyakulam block in Theni district, Thiru G. Kathamani, a progressive mango grower successfully adopted this technology in Alphonso. Regular supervision and visits by the scientists to provide technical inputs and plant protection measures helped him to adopt the technology in Imam Pasand as well. In Imam Pasand (6 yrs old), from 4 hectares he harvested 72.50 kg/tree in with a benefit cost ratio of 4.4:1. With the adoption of this technology, he has become role model and had helped in spreading it through the Mango Growers Association of Theni District. Now more farmers are now adopting the practice in Tamil Nadu and currently, the adoption of the technology is seen in more than 110 hectares in Theni, Madurai, Dindigul and Virudhunagar districts of Tamil Nadu in different varieties of mango.

In Bodinayakkanur block, Thiru. Hasan Mohammed has adopted this pruning technology along with paclobutrazol application in mango cv. Alphonso for achieving higher productivity from his 14 acres of orchard under HDP at the spacing of 5 x 5 m with a benefit cost ratio of 4.8:1. In Virudhunagar district, Thiru. A. Samarasam, a progressive mango grower is regularly adopting pruning technology along with paclobutrazol application for his alphonso mango trees. Mr. Pandian, mango grower of Manjalar village of Periyakulam taluk has adopted pruning technology to high density planting mango var. Alphonso (5 x 5 m) and got 89 to 90 kg per tree (7 years old) for an area of 4.5 hectares. Nearly, 275 mango growers in southern parts of Tamilnadu are practicing this technology to enhance the yield and quality of mango Cv. Alphonso.

Farmers Contact Details:

Thiru G. Kathamani, Sothuparai, Periyakulam, Theni District. Mobile: 9443331764

With inputs from the ICAR-AICRP Centre, Periyakulam

Grape Variety ARI-516

In Maharashtra, grapes are grown mostly for table purpose. Thompson seedless and its clones like Manik Chaman, Sonaka, Tas-A-Ganesh are popular in white varieties and Kismish Cherni with its clones like Sharad seedless, black sonaka are popular varieties among grape growers. Growing grapes for juice purpose is recent concept for grape growers in Maharashtra. Growing varieties for juice purpose is always profitable provided value addition is done by processing it into juice. Moreover, cost of cultivation of ARI -516 is less as no growth hormones are required as well as it is moderately resistant to downy and powdery mildew.

Mr. Kabade, a progressive farmer from Miraj area had taken 50 cuttings of our variety ARI 516 and planted on his farm situated at Miraj from Sangli district of Maharashtra on 18th Oct. 2013. He found the variety resistant to downy and powdery mildew and profusely yielding, about 10 kg/vine in second year itself. Within next year he increased the area of plantation to 3 acres. In the current year 2017, he sold one ton grapes at the rate of Rs. 35/-per Kg to another progressive farmer Mr. Prabhakar Wagh having wine making unit near Nasik (Shivprasad wines, Ranwad Post, Niphad Taluk, Nasik) who processed it into grape juice. Next year Mr. Kabade plans to make juice by himself.

The variety ARI-516 is recommended for juice purpose. After the recommendation of AICRP, it has started spreading in Maharashtra. Maharashtra Rajya Draksha Bagaitdar Sangh (MRDBS) which is the largest co-operative society having 28,000 members is involved in promotion of this variety.

Farmers Contact Details:

Sri. Baburao Anna Kabade, #1952, Malgaon Tal. Miraj, Dist. Sangli Malgaon- Sangli MH 416407. Mobile Number: 9922111694

With inputs from Dr. Sujata Tetali, Late S. G. Patil, Mrs. S.P. Karkamkar Mr. Phalake, Dr. MIS Gill, Agharkar Research Institute, Pune.

Baburao Anna Kabade